

Effect of Some Thiocompounds on the Corrosion of 3S Aluminium in Hydrochloric Acid Solutions

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Inhibitory action of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate and its decomposition product, carbon disulphide towards corrosion of 3S aluminium in 0.5N and 1.0N hydrochloric acid has been investigated. Both the compounds are found very effective at 30° temp. At 40° and 60° their inhibitive power remarkably decreased. Both the electrodes were polarized but cathodic polarization was found remarkable when external current is applied. The inhibition afforded by these compounds may be due to adsorption. Adsorption isotherms plotted ($\log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \rightarrow \log C$) as straight lines were observed. The value of heat of adsorption was also calculated.

ALTHOUGH aluminium is unaffected by nitric acid, it is corroded by other mineral acids.

Looking to the increasing usage of aluminium and aluminium based alloys, a study of inhibition of the corrosion of aluminium is a problem of paramount importance. Hydrochloric acid is one of those acids which attack aluminium vigorously¹⁻⁵. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to evaluate the inhibitory action of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate and its decomposition product, carbon disulphide towards corrosion of 3S aluminium in 0.5 and 1.0 N hydrochloric acid solutions at different temperatures.

Experimental

The aluminium alloy (S.W.G. 22, 1/2 hard) used had the following composition: Al-98, Cu-0.15, Mn-1.0, Fe-0.75 and Si-0.6% (maximum). Rectangular specimens of size 3×6 cm were used. The preparation, testing and cleaning procedures for specimens adopted were those described by Champion⁶. Hydrochloric acid solution (250 ml) was taken for the immersion of each specimen. Experiments were carried out at 30°, 50° and 60°. Reproducibility of the inhibitive efficiency values obtained was ±2%.

For the galvanostatic studies, the specimens had an effective area of 4 sq. cm (size 2×2 cm). The procedure adopted for the potential measurements was the same as described by Gatos⁷.

Results

Weight loss data are given in Tables 1 and 2. Results of polarization studies are represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (Na-DDC): In 0.5 N HCl, Na-DDC acted as an excellent inhibitor at 1 day duration; the inhibitive power falling off at lower concentration. At 2-days duration, in hydrochloric acid it mostly acted as an excellent inhibitor.¹

TABLE I

INHIBITION OF CORROSION OF 3S ALUMINIUM IN 0.5N HCl				
Size: 3×6 cm		Temperature: 30°±1°		
Concentration of inhibitor %	1 Day		2 Days	
	Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %
0.0	1130	—	1230	—
<i>Na-DDC</i>				
0.005	55.0	95	885.0	28
0.01	52.0	95	646.0	47
0.025	48.0	96	82.0	93
0.05	43.0	96	75.0	94
0.1	35.0	97	62.0	95
<i>CS₂</i>				
0.05	48.0	96	102.0	92
0.1	40.0	96	77.0	95
0.25	30.0	97	57.0	95
0.5	30.0	97	55.0	95
1.0	28.0	97	51.0	96

Na-DDC was found to be a fair corrosion inhibitor for 3S aluminium in 1.0 N HCl, at 50°, the inhibitive power increasing with increase in its concentration. A remarkable fall in inhibition was noted at 60 min duration and 60°.

The results of galvanostatic measurement showed that in the case of Na-DDC, both the electrodes were

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Fig. 1. Influence of current densities on anode and cathode potential.

AA'—0.5 N HCl. BB'—0.5 N HCl+0.1% sodium diethyldithiocarbamate. CC'—0.5 N HCl+1.0% Carbon disulphide.

Fig. 2. Langmuir absorption isotherms of 3S aluminium in 1.0 N HCl solution for sodium diethyldithiocarbamate.

AA'—1/2 hour for 50°; BB'—1 hour for 50°; A'A'—1/2 hour for 60°; B'B'—1 hour for 60°.

polarized but cathodic polarization being high at low current density and a sudden increase in cathodic potential was observed.

Carbon disulphide (CS₂): Carbon disulphide acted as an excellent inhibitor at all concentrations at both the durations in both the acid solutions. Carbon disulphide was found to be a poor inhibitor at higher temperatures. Its inhibitive power decreased at 50°.

The results of galvanostatic measurement showed that in the case of carbon disulphide both the elec-

trodes were polarized, but cathodic polarization was quite remarkable.

Discussion

The inhibitive poves of Na-DDC has been attributed to its decomposition products, carbon disulphide, by acid^{8,9}. The mechanism of its decomposition in acid is given below :

The nature of inhibition at elevated temperature is very similar to that obtained with carbon disulphide at lower concentraton showing that it is carbon disulphide which also appears to be responsible for the inhibition exhibited by Na-DDC. Carbon disulphide is a liquid with a very low B.P. (46.3°). The result is that its inhibition decreases very rapidly with increase in the temperature. The inhibitive power falls off very rapidly particularly at its lower concentrations.

TABLE 2—INHIBITION OF CORROSION OF 3S ALUMINIUM IN 1.0 N HCL

Concentration of inhibition %	30°				50°				60°			
	1 hour		2 hours		1/2 hour		1 hour		1/2 hour		1 hour	
	L	I	L	I	L	I	L	I	L	I	L	I
0.0	475	—	1340	—	450	—	1250	—	810	—	1450	—
Na-DDC												
0.005	34.0	93	75.0	94	171.0	62	1170	7	636	21	1342	7
0.01	26.0	95	67.0	96	145.0	68	1074	14	629	22	1332	8
0.025	20.0	96	50.0	97	126.0	72	693	45	470	42	1099	24
0.05	18.0	96	40.0	97	110.0	76	460	63	392	52	891	39
0.1	17.0	96	30.0	98	81.0	82	336	73	313	61	655	55
CS₂												
0.05	17.0	96	49.0	96	294.0	35	1101	12	660	31	1276	12
0.1	18.0	96	51.0	96	243.0	46	1060	15	552	32	1271	12
0.25	15.0	97	39.0	97	207.0	54	731	42	531	34	1227	15
0.5	15.0	97	39.0	97	198.0	56	660	47	479	41	1039	28
1.0	15.0	97	30.0	98	175.0	61	497	76	415	49	1004	31

In the cases of Na-DDC and CS₂ the polarization data revealed that at 30° it is only the cathode which is polarized. The anodic polarization was found less as compared to the cathodic polarization.

Adsorption characteristics :

Hoar and Holiday¹⁰ studied the inhibitive action of substituted thioureas as corrosion inhibitors for the acid dissolution of mild steel at 70°. They found that for some inhibitors the results were in reasonable agreement with the Langmuir isotherm. The results of the present investigation are for a very wide range of values of C , the equation is best applied in the following form

$$\log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = \log A + \log C - \frac{Q}{2.3 RT}$$

where θ is the fraction of active sites of the metal surface covered by adsorbed inhibitor, so that: $(1-\theta)$ is the fraction of the active sites, reacting with the solutions. 'A' is a temperature independent constant, C is the inhibitor concentration (in molarity) and is the heat of adsorption. If the equation

applies, the variation of $\log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta}$ with $\log C$ should be

linear, with a gradient of unity at any temperature T , provided that $\log A$ and Q are constant over the range of concentration involved. The work of Hoar and Holliday was extended by Hoar and Khera¹¹. They found that the use of simple model of adsorption agreed well with the expression

$$\log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = \log C + 3.08.$$

Results of percentage inhibition agree well with the Langmuir adsorption isotherm (Fig. 2 and 3). In the present work inhibition studies were carried

out at different temperatures i.e., 50° and 60°. The inhibition given by most of the compounds studied is mainly due to adsorption. If a straight line is

Fig. 3. Langmuir adsorption isotherms of 3S aluminium in 1.0 N HCl solution for carbondisulphide.

AA—1/2 hour for 50°; BB—1 hour for 50°; A'A'—1/2 hour for 60°; B'B'—1 hour for 60°.

obtained, when $\log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \rightarrow \log C$ graph is plotted, one can calculate the heat of adsorption. In the present cases Q is calculated as follows :

$$Q = 4.6 \left(\log \frac{\theta_2}{1-\theta_2} - \log \frac{\theta_1}{1-\theta_1} \right) \left(\frac{T_1 \times T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \right)$$

where R is gas constant

$$R = 1.987 \text{ cal. deg}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$$

$$T_1 = 273 + 50 = 323^\circ\text{K}$$

$$T_2 = 273 + 60 = 333^\circ\text{K}$$

The values of heat of adsorption (Q) remain in the range of 14 to 43 K.Cal.gm⁻¹.mole⁻¹.

	$\frac{1}{2}$ hour	1 hour	
Na-DDC	33.860	32.160	K.Cal.gm ⁻¹ .mole ⁻¹
CS ₂	14.880	43.040	K.Cal.gm ⁻¹ .mole ⁻¹

This leads to the conclusion that at most of the inhibitor are adsorbed on the metal surface by chemisorption.

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